

IMPACT OF USING I-BOOST IN BROILER DRINKING WATER ON IMMUNITY, SERUM BIOCHEMICAL AND ANTIOXIDANT ENZYMES

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Abstract

This study was conducted to evaluate the effect of a specific herbal extract (I-Boost) on some biochemical, hormonal, immunological, and antioxidant enzymes in the drinking water of the broiler. A total of 204 one-day chicks (Ross 308) were used within three treatments. Each treatment was including four replicates (17 chicks/replicate). The first treatment was control (T1) and had no I-Boost product in the drinking water. The second (T2) and third (T3) were containing 1 ml/L and 2 ml/L of I-Boost in drinking water, respectively. The chicks in T2 and T3 were given the product three consecutive days per week from day one to 35 days. Commercial feed was provided ad-libitum during the entire trial. On day 35, serum biochemical, IgG against ND and IBV, and antioxidant enzymes were measured. The results showed the addition of I-Boost in broiler drinking water has significantly increased the total IgG against IBV and ND diseases. Treatments had no significant effects on serum lipids parameters except for VLDL and triglyceride. Both serum total protein and globulin were significantly increased with the addition of I-Boost into drinking water. Thyroid hormone (T4) was significantly affected by this product while it did not affect the T3 level. Similarly, liver enzyme AST was significantly decreased in treated groups but ALT was not affected. The addition of I-Boost into drinking water significantly decreased serum glucose, uric acid, and creatine kinase. All of the studied serum antioxidant enzymes (TAC, SOD, CAT, GPx, and) were improved. It was concluded that the addition of 1ml/L and 2ml/L of I-Boost product into broiler drinking water improved the general biochemical, immunological, and antioxidant enzymes in broiler chicken.

Keywords: Broiler; Herbal extract; I-Boost; Antioxidant; Immunity

INTRODUCTION

With the use of feed additives, it is possible to alter the microbial habitat and gastrointestinal function of domestic animals, hence enhancing growth and feed efficiency (Collington et al., 1990). About 80% of livestock have been provided synthetic substances for growth promotion or medicine (Lee et al., 2001). But recently discovered antibiotic-resistant bacterial types could seriously endanger public health (Rafeeq et al., 2021). Researchers are investigating substitute agents such as organic acids, enzymes, and phytochemical feed additives like spices and herb plants and products generated from them as a result of the ban on antibiotic use in farm animals (Diarra and Malouin, 2014; Pandey et al., 2019). Alternatives that could be employed in the production of broilers include medicinal plants and the extracts and essential oils they produce (Wati et al., 2015). Indeed, complex bioactive substances such as flavonoids, phenolic, steroids, coumarins, lipids, purines, and monoterpenoids are abundant in phytochemical additions (Brisibe et al., 2008). Plant extracts can support both

general performance and health state (Janssen, 1989; Manzanilla et al., 2001). The enhancement of native digestive enzyme discharge, activation of the immunological response, and antiviral, antioxidant, and antihelminthic effects could all have a good impact on the health and performance of animals (Omer et al., 2016).

Thyme (*Thymus vulgaris* L.), a well-known medicinal plant grown primarily in Mediterranean countries, is one of the herbal plants that has drawn more attention because of its anti-inflammatory and antibacterial properties. Additionally, it has been claimed that the herb possesses anti-bacterial properties against a variety of harmful microorganisms (Varel, 2002). Thymol and carvacrol, two of the main ingredients in thyme essential oil, have both been found to have strong antioxidant effects (Toghyani et al., 2010). According to these researchers, thyme powder at a 10 g/kg level considerably ($P < 0.05$) enhanced HDL-Cholesterol concentration. Sigolo et al., (2021) indicated that a 300 mg/L dose of thyme supplementation may enhance blood serum measurements.

In the past, biliary disorders and other gastrointestinal tract diseases were treated with the medicinal plant *Silybum marianum* (SM). The active components in this plant include substances that are flavonoid, resinous and oily substances. The three flavonoids silybin, silychristin, and silydianin—collectively known as silymarin are the most significant flavonoids in SM fruit (Tyler et al., 1997; Omidbiagi, 2005). Silymarin lowers blood cholesterol and fat levels and has anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties. Additionally, atherosclerosis risk was decreased and the immunological response was seen to be improved (Gupta et al., 2000; Horvath et al., 2001). Results of numerous pieces of research have demonstrated that silymarin boosts the immune system, decreases cholesterol, protects the liver from cirrhosis, and increases performance in broilers (Chand et al., 2011; Tedesco et al., 2004). Supplemental SM seeds decreased cholesterol levels and ALT and aspartate aminotransferase enzyme activity (AST). Supplementing with SM caused the liver's lipid content to drop and its glycogen levels to rise (Suchy et al., 2008).

Numerous phytochemicals, such as polysaccharides, flavonoids, peptides, alkaloids, phenolic acids, and terpenes are present in dandelion plants (Qian et al., 2014), it provides a variety of nutrients and biologically active compounds (Qureshi et al., 2017). Studies have found that the essential oil of the dandelion plant contains a significant amount of inulin (Inulin), estimated at 40%, which is a complex sugar that has recently been used as a prebiotic. These compounds work to preserve the microbial balance within the gut as it is thought to be a type of ideal compounds that motivate the growth propagation of beneficial bacteria like (*Bifidobacterium* and *Lactobacilli*), which is a high significance for health and immunity (Torshizi et al., 2004). According to Noor et al. (2021), the triglyceride and blood glucose levels of the treated birds with dandelion significantly decreased ($P < 0.05$), while the concentrations of cholesterol and glutathione peroxidase in the blood serum significantly increased ($P < 0.05$). Therefore, this study is aimed to investigate the effect of adding various levels of I-Boost, a herbal compound, into the drinking water of a broiler on serum biochemical, immunity response, and antioxidant enzymes.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Experimental design

This experiment was carried out in commercial poultry house conditions. The total number of day-old chicks used in this research was 204 (Ross 308). Each replicate's initial weight was determined on the first day, and the chicks were divided evenly and randomly among the various treatments as follows:

T1 control (no additive in drinking water).

T2 adding I-Boost in drinking water (1m/1 litter) for 3 consecutive days per week.

T3 adding I-Boost in drinking water (2m/1 litter) for 3 consecutive days per week.

Each treatment consisted of four replicates with 17 chicks each. For raising throughout the entire study period, floor pens were utilized. The raising halls were furnished with the necessary equipment, such as heating systems and programmable thermostats (Table 1). From 1 to 35 days, the chicks were given an ad-libitum diet consisting of a commercial diet (Table 2).

Table 1: The temperature of the rearing hall

Age	Temperature degree °C
1 st week	34-35
2 nd week	32-33
3 rd week	29-30
4 th week	27-28
5 th week	26-27

Vaccination program

Newcastle disease and infectious bronchitis vaccines were sprayed on day-old chicks. Chicks were given the vaccination in drinking water against Newcastle infections at 17 and 27 days of age. All vaccinations came from the Czech Republic.

Serum biochemical parameters.

The serum parameters were examined at 35 days of age following Mustafa et al., (2021). Two birds in the same cage had their blood drawn from the jugular vein, and the samples were kept cool until they were transported to the lab. The whole blood was thereafter centrifuged at 1500 g for ten minutes to prepare the serum samples, which were then stored at -20 oC. For estimation of lipid profile, thyroid hormones, glucose, protein profile, ALT, and AST, the auto analyzer (Cobas 6000, Roche Diagnostics, Germany) was utilized.

Immunological Tests

Using particular OVATEC® Plus and SERELISA® Rabies kits from Synbiotic (USA), antibodies titration was measured against infectious bronchitis (IB) and Newcastle disease (ND) using ELISA.

Table 2: Ingredient of the diet used in the experiment

Ingredient	Kg/ton	
	Starter	Grower
Yellow Corn	426.5	460
Wheat	100	100
Wheat bran	40	40
Soya bean meal (46%)	370	340
Vegetable Oil	20	22
Limestone	2	2
Di calcium phosphate	13	10
DL- methionine	0.5	0.5
Lysin	0.5	0.5
Anti-toxin (toxbond)	1	1
Anti-coccidia(salinomycin)	0.250	0.250
Salt	1.5	1.5
Premix	25	25
Analysed chemical composition		
Crude protein (%)	22.64	21.48
Energy ME/kg diet	2923	3050
Fat %	4.12	4.43
Linoleic acid %	2.04	2.19
Crude fibre %	2.93	2.92
Methionine %	0.50	0.49
Lysine%	1.52	1.43
Tryptophan %	0.40	0.38
Meth. + cystine %	0.84	0.81
Arginine %	1.60	1.51
Threonine %	1.02	1.04
Calcium %	1.04	0.95
Available phosphorus %	0.47	0.42
Sodium %	0.18	0.19
Chloride %	0.21	0.18
Aflatoxin (ppb)	1	5.4
Ochratoxin (ppb)	0.2	1.4
T2 toxin(ppb)	43.6	38.3

Statistical analysis

The data were prepared for analysis using a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet. The SAS statistical software package was then used to analyze the data. Later, the significance of the major

impacts was determined using the SAS software (PROC GLM) (SAS, 2013). Duncan's multiple range tests were performed to find variations among individual treatment means.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 3: Effect of adding different levels of I-Boost in broiler drinking water on antibodies titer against infectious bronchitis and Newcastle disease at 35 days of age

Variables	Treatments			SEM	P value
	T1	T2	T3		
Infectious bronchitis	901.87 ^c	1930.03 ^b	2282.13 ^a	127.29	0.0001
Newcastle disease	7767.88 ^b	10469.05 ^a	10975.63 ^a	346.91	0.0001

The effect of adding different doses of I-boost in drinking water on broiler serum antibody titer against infectious bronchitis and Newcastle disease at 35 days of age is shown in Table 3. Antibody titer for IBV and ND was significantly higher ($p < 0.0001$) in broilers that had I-Boost in their drinking water compared to the control group. Additionally, IBV antibody titer was significantly higher in T3 than in the other two treated groups. Similar results were obtained by Ahmed et al., (2020) in which the antibody titer against ND was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) in the broiler group fed 15g/kg of herbal additive (*Silybum marianum*). Moreover, our results agree with those found by Sadeghi et al., (2012) who obtained higher antibody titer against ND in broiler had a mixture of herbal powder. Qureshi et al., (2017) stated that Phagocytic stimulation, which is crucial for reducing viral infection, replication, and spread, can be greatly aided by herbal medicines or botanicals with immunomodulatory effects. However, Rafeeq et al., (2020) found no significant variation in antibody titer when they fed broiler herbal products.

Table 4: Effect of adding different levels of I-boost in broiler drinking water on serum lipids profile of broiler at 35 days of age

Variables	Treatments			SEM	P value
	T1	T2	T3		
Cholesterol (mg/dl)	140.62	139.85	136.75	1.18	0.368
High density lipoprotein (mg/dl)	63.87	62.63	63.37	0.67	0.762
Low density lipoprotein (mg/dl)	38.87	37.25	36.25	0.85	0.471
Very low-density lipoprotein (mg/dl)	7.70 ^a	6.30 ^b	6.07 ^b	0.17	0.0001
Triglycerides	38.50 ^a	31.50 ^b	30.37 ^b	0.88	0.0001

The effect of adding different doses of I-boost in broiler drinking water on serum lipid profile broiler performance from 1 to 35 days of age is shown in Table 4. The results show that adding this product to the broiler drinking water had no significant effect among all groups on Cholesterol, High-Density Lipoprotein (HDL), and Low-Density Lipoprotein (LDL) levels. However, both Very Low-Density Lipoprotein (VLDL) and triglyceride were

significantly ($p < 0.0001$) reduced in groups (T2 and T3) compared to the control group. No alterations in cholesterol, high-density lipoprotein, or low-density lipoprotein were seen by Afshin et al. (2017) which is agreeing with the present findings. These results are in partial agreement with the findings by Noor et al., (2021) who found a significant reduction ($p < 0.05$) in both triglyceride and cholesterol levels in the broiler-fed dandelion leaf powder compared to the control group. Although the LDL result found by Toghyani et al., (2010) agrees with our results, they claimed significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher HDL level and no significant variation in triglyceride in broiler-fed thyme powder (10 g/kg).

Table 5: Effect of adding different levels of I-boost in broiler drinking water on serum protein profile of broiler at 35 days of age

Variables	Treatments			SEM	P value
	T1	T2	T3		
Total protein (mg/dl)	2.49 b	2.99 a	3.15 a	0.079	0.0003
Albumin (mg/dl)	1.19	1.18	1.20	0.013	0.894
Globulin (mg/dl)	1.30 b	1.80 a	1.95 a	0.077	0.0002

The effect of adding I-boost in drinking water on the serum protein profile of the broiler at 35 days is shown in Table (5). Both total protein and globulin levels were affected by adding I-Boost into drinking water and therefore, they were significantly ($p < 0.0005$) higher compared to the control group. However, there were no statistical effects of the used herbal product on albumin levels among all groups. These results are in total agreement with those found by Hassan et al., (2016) when they fed broiler different *Moringa oleifera* leaves meal. They claimed a significant increase in both total protein and globulin levels and no significant differences in albumin levels. According to Melesse et al., (2013) increased total proteins in chickens given the I boost in the drinking water may be due to a more active metabolism of the proteins in the chicken's organ. Additionally, the present measurements are in partial agreement with the results obtained by Rafeeq et al., (2021) who found no significant variation in albumin levels in broiler-fed broiler two herbal extracts. However, their findings disagree within which there were no significant differences in total protein and globulin levels.

Table 6: Effect of adding different levels of I-boost in broiler drinking water on serum thyroid hormone and liver enzyme AST and ALT of broiler at 35 days of age

Variables	Treatments			SEM	P value
	T1	T2	T3		
T4 (nmol/ml)	24.07 c	26.04 b	30.76 a	0.61	0.0001
T3 (nmol/ml)	2.04	2.02	2.06	0.013	0.650
AST (U/L)	251.87 a	215.37 b	221.37 b	4.09	0.0001
ALT (U/L)	3.87	3.76	3.80	0.053	0.731

Impact of using different doses of I-boost in broiler drinking water on serum thyroid hormone and liver enzyme AST and ALT of broiler at 35 days of age is shown in Table 6. In the

results, I Boost administration significantly affected the T4 level but there had no significant effect on the T3 level. Similarly, there was a significant decrease in the AST level in broiler serum had I boost compared to the control group, but there wasn't any significant effect of adding I boost into drinking water on the ALT level in broiler serum. Qaid et al., (2021) agree with the T3 and ALT results found in this study in which there was no significant variation in T3 and ALT levels when they fed broilers with different levels of cinnamon. However, our T4 and AST findings are in disagreement with their study achievements. The high antioxidant content, especially vitamin C, which can lessen the negative effects of heat stress and improve the physiological responses of birds to heat stress, may be the cause of the elevation in T3 levels (Hassan et al., 2016). Rafeeq et al., (2020) indicated that adding cumin to the broiler diet significantly decreased the AST enzyme level and had no effect on the ALT level which agreed with the present results. They stated that decreasing the liver enzyme (AST) in the serum indicates the safety of the used herbal in the broiler diet. Similar results were found by Hassan et al., (2016) when they fed broiler *Moringa oleifera* Leaves.

Table 7: Effect of adding different levels of I-boost in broiler drinking water on serum glucose, uric acid, and creatine kinase of broiler at 35 days of age

Variables	Treatments			SEM	P value
	T1	T2	T3		
Glucose (mg/dl)	232.75 a	210.00 b	206.87 b	3.43	0.0009
Uric acid (mg/dl)	5.47 a	4.63 b	4.37 b	0.116	0.0001
Creatine kinase (U/L)	5152.25 a	4143.88 b	4149.02 b	106.12	0.0001

The impact of using different doses of I-boost in broiler drinking water on serum glucose, uric acid, and creatine kinase of broiler at 35 days of age is shown in table (7). All of the studied parameters in this table were significantly decreased in both treatments in which the I-Boost was added to drinking water compared to the control group. Noor et al., () found a similar glucose trend when they fed broiler dandelion which indicated that this plant significantly decreased the glucose level in the blood in the broiler group fed dandelion plant powder. A decrease in the glucose level may be due to an active compound found in this plant which leads to an increase in insulin level and therefore decrease the glucose level (Hussain et al., 2004). Significant improvements in uric acid and creatine kinase are good indicators of renal function improvement in blood purification as the total protein was significantly higher in the treated group compared to the control (Table 5) (Abd El-Hady et al., 2020). However, the present results are in disagreement with those found by Abd El-Hady et al., (2020) and Qaid et al., (2021) who didn't find any significant effect of the different herbal extracts on uric acid and/or creatine kinase.

Figure 1: Effect of various levels of I-Boost product on serum antioxidant of broiler. (A) Total Antioxidants (ng/dl), (B) Superoxide dismutase (nl/ml), (C) serum glutathione peroxidase (nl/ml), (D) serum Catalase (nl/ml)

The influence of adding different levels of I-Boost product in broiler drinking water on some of the serum antioxidants is shown in figure (1). The results showed that providing the I-Boost in drinking water had improved all the measured serum antioxidants compared to the control group. Both levels of I-Boost (T2 and T3) had almost increased by 75% of the antioxidants (TAC, SOD, and GPx) and 100% (CAT) in the broiler serum compared to the control group. Similar results were published by Albarrak (2021) who provided the broiler *Rhazya stricta* in the drinking water and found significant improvement in both TAC, SOD ($p < 0.05$), and CAT ($p < 0.01$). Results of Abd El-Hady et al., (2020) agree with our results in which they found a significant improvement in TAC of broiler provided the thymol in the

drinking water. However, Ahmed et al., (2000) and Ahmed et al., (2006) showed no effect of specific herbal supplements on SOD and GPx in the broiler. This may be due to different animal strains, ages, and physiological conditions (Zhang et al., (2009). Free radicals are created during regular metabolism, but if they are produced in large enough quantities, they can cause physical harm to the organism. The three primary antioxidant enzymes in neutralizing the oxygen free radical are SOD, GSHPx, and catalase (McCord, 1979). According to a significant amount of research, plant polyphenolic flavonoids are one of the main classes of chemicals that operate as fundamental antioxidant free-radical terminators (Huang and Frankel, 1997; Singh et al., 2005). Subsequently, the I-Boost product contains a significant amount of flavonoids.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the overall results showed that the addition of the I-Boost herbal product had improved most of the studied serum biochemical, immunological, and enzymatic status in the broiler. Both of the added levels (1ml/L and 2ml/L) of I-Boost increased the IgG and serum antioxidant levels which can be considered a dependable principle of broiler performance.

DECLARATION OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there are no competing interests that might have influenced the current work.

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